

“Involta” Ilmiy Jurnalni

Vebsayt: <https://involta.uz/>

INFORMATION ABOUT ENGLISH LESSONS AT SCHOOL IMPORTANCE OF USING TECHNOLOGIES DURING CLASSES: PROBLEM AND SOLUTION

Abdulahatova Mohichehra G'olibjon qizi

Namangan state university, second-year student

Sherova Orzigul Alisher qizi

Uzbekistan state world languages university, second-year student:

Xakimova Dilshoda Oybek qizi

Uzbekistan state world languages university, second-year student:

ANNOTATSIYA: Maqolada kunning dolzarb mavzusiga aylangan o'zaro fanlararo bog'liqlik, ayniqsa, informatika va chet tili o'qitish metodikasining o'zaro uzviy bog'liqliklari boshlang'ich sinflar doirasida afzallik taraflari yoritib berilgan. Interaktiv metodlar asosida til ko'nikmalarini yanada keng yoritish qoidalari ifodalangan.

Kalit so'z: texnologiya, o'qitish metodikasi, multimediya, psixologik to'siq, samaradorlik.

АННОТАЦИЯ: Междисциплинарная взаимозависимость, особенности информатики, ставшая актуальной проблемой в статье и взаимосвязи

методики обучения иностранному языку выделяются в начальных классах, желательно. Выражены правила более широкого охвата языковых навыков на основе интерактивных методов.

Ключевые слова: технология, методы обучения, мультимедиа, психологический барьер, эффективность.

ANNOTATION: Interdisciplinary interdependence, especially informatics, which has become a topical issue in the article and the interrelationships of foreign language teaching methodology are highlighted within the primary grades, preferably. The rules of broader coverage of language skills on the basis of interactive methods expressed.

Keywords: technology, teaching methods, multimedia, psychological barrier, effectiveness.

Today, it is important and reasonable to study a particular foreign language, especially in certain areas of technology and in connection with it, based on the balance of all areas. In today's rapidly evolving world, the methodology of teaching a foreign language has been growing rapidly, especially in the last decade. It is very important that the learner understands the essence of teachers' teaching and consciously implements different language teaching techniques while also being able to see their essence. An English teacher has a great responsibility, which is to have not only the knowledge and skills, but also enough modern knowledge to arouse the interest of the younger generation.

With a thorough knowledge of student psychology, students of any age need to know what motivating spirit they can awaken, what they need to bring into the classroom, and most importantly, how they can positively influence on their worldview. We know that the younger generation today cannot imagine life without computer technology. Therefore, the role of multimedia in foreign language teaching is invaluable. According to academic researchers, the best method in linguistics, and especially in foreign language teaching, is not recognized, and no method in foreign language teaching can be a guide to other methods. In today's modern age,

information and technology, globalization and commercialization, English language is not only our main topic of education today, but also occupy a central position. ICT - Information and communication technology is becoming the most important part of our lives today.

The demand for learning a foreign language is also growing day by day. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in these educational processes. Teaching through multimedia provides great opportunities for the educator. In this way, it is possible to raise the interest of children to a high level and keep their attention for a long time. Through this, we can see that the children's language skills have further increased. If our topic is "Animals", we first use their sounds to teach the names of different animals. The children pay close attention to this, and immediately begin to say the names of the animals as cat? Tiger? Bear? The development of language ability at an early age is mainly shaped by constant imitation, and many roles often appear through imitation in cartoons, so when watching a cartoon, we can see changes in children's movements.

Therefore, we can use the cartoon as an effective educational tool, which helps to increase the educational effectiveness of children. Nowadays, some parents are very concerned about children's interest in cartoons, but in fact, their fantasy in the development of young children serves as a key factor in shaping their worldview. Teaching tools are important in teaching a foreign language in high school. There are various teaching tools. The use of tools helps to understand quickly, to understand consciously, to keep the memory well. Teaching tools are part of a complex teaching system. G. V. Rogova has been teaching English lately. He spoke about the widespread use of teaching aids and teaching materials and described them as follows: Teaching aids that we mean different types of such objects in the fall, from which we derive English language materials. We use it to present to swimmers, to strengthen their minds, to develop skills, abilities, to test.

Among the most effective approaches to foreign language teaching is the use of information and communication technologies, language teaching methods in distance learning. There is a wide range of opportunities for language learning using computer technology, especially the INTERNET.

They are manifested in the following:

- 1) to actively use in practice the knowledge and skills acquired in oral communication in a foreign language, to learn to use the acquired language materials not only in his speech, but also in understanding the speech of the interlocutor, whom he met on the Internet;
- 2) to develop the ability to adapt the acquired speech knowledge to the changing situations of the relationship;
- 3) to create a strong, immediate motivation and motivation for a realistic approach to the organization of the conversation, the study of speech, which takes place in the form of informal communication;
- 4) overcoming psychological barriers, in particular, the fear of speaking a foreign language and making mistakes, the loss of the barrier, as well as internal and external tension and embarrassment;

In short, the study of foreign languages is one of the urgent tasks of our time, and it is one of the urgent tasks of scientists and teachers to develop and recommend intensive methods of language teaching to the younger generation. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, and all other goals (education, upbringing, development) are realized in the process of achieving this main goal. The communicative approach involves the study of communication and the formation of the ability to interact between cultures, which is the basis of Internet activity.

REFERENCES:

1. N. Q. Khatamova, M. N. Mirzayeva. 'Interactive methods used in English lessons' (manual). Navoi. 2006. 40 pages.
2. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rixsittilayeva. 'Use of aids in foreign language teaching'.
3. www.goaravtisyanyan.ru
4. U. H. Hoshimov, I.Ya.Yokubov. 'Methods of teaching English in secondary schools'. Tashkent. 'Teacher'. 1993. 40-41-pages.